

To what extent does promotion of TCM contribute to the cultivation of China's soft power: Evidence from Covid-19 and the Belt and Road Initiative.

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Abstract

This study examines whether Traditional Chinese Medicine (TCM) is being utilised as a tool through which China cultivates soft power. In contemporary China, the regulation and international promotion of TCM are closely linked to state policy, placing the Chinese government in a unique position to shape its global expansion. As China has increasingly promoted TCM abroad, particularly through the Belt and Road Initiative (BRI) and through medical assistance during the Covid-19 pandemic, questions arise regarding the broader political implications of this development.

Drawing on theories of soft power, this study analyses how TCM is incorporated into China's foreign policy and international engagement. Two case studies are examined: the promotion of TCM during the Covid-19 pandemic and the integration of TCM into the BRI. The findings suggest that TCM functions not only as a medical practice but also as a cultural and diplomatic instrument through which China seeks to enhance its international image and influence.

Key words: soft power, TCM, BRI, Covid-19, China

Traditional Chinese Medicine: Historical and Contemporary Debates

During the twentieth and twenty-first centuries, numerous epidemics and pandemics have posed significant threats to global public health. Their emergence has prompted the development of new treatments and cures, advancing scientific research and leading to major breakthroughs in biomedicine. Alongside these developments, alternative medical approaches such as Traditional Chinese Medicine (TCM) have also been proposed as potential treatments. However, the acceptance of TCM remains largely limited to countries such as Japan and South Korea, where elements of traditional medicine have already been integrated into national healthcare systems (Cheung, 2011).

At present, TCM remains the subject of considerable debate and controversy across scientific, environmental, and political arenas. One of the primary sources of controversy concerns the methods by which TCM is studied and evaluated. Critics argue that many TCM treatments lack evidence-based medical validation, particularly randomised controlled trials, which are considered a fundamental standard in modern biomedical research (Hesketh and Zhu, 1997; Leung et al., 2006; Tang, 2006; Tang et al., 1999). Concerns have also been raised

regarding inconsistent efficacy and the potential for severe side effects (Stone, 2008). In addition, the conceptual foundations of TCM differ substantially from those of Western biomedicine. While Western medicine typically focuses on diagnosing and treating specific diseases, TCM emphasises the overall balance and health of the body as an integrated system (Hesketh and Zhu, 1997; Keji and Hao, 2003; Sun et al., 2013). TCM is therefore often characterised as a preventative approach to health rather than a method for curing individual illnesses (Xu and Xia, 2019). These conceptual differences reflect broader distinctions in medical philosophy and practice.

Prior to the development of modern European clinical medicine in the nineteenth century, Chinese medicine was already deeply embedded within Chinese civilisation and healthcare systems. At the beginning of the twentieth century, Chinese medicine also possessed a substantial body of recorded pharmacological knowledge. Consequently, socio-cultural factors must be considered when analysing the role and development of TCM (Hongjun, 1991; Unschuld, 1987).

Further controversies extend beyond questions of efficacy and differing medical paradigms. TCM has also been associated with environmental concerns, particularly its role in the global wildlife trade. Some scholars describe TCM as a “significant driver” of illicit wildlife trafficking (Byard, 2016; Ellis, 2013). The use of exotic animal products in certain traditional medicines has contributed to illegal wildlife markets estimated to generate \$10–20 billion annually (Wilson-Wilde, 2010). Approximately ten per cent of traditional Chinese medicines contain ingredients derived from animals such as tigers, rhinoceroses, freshwater turtles, and pangolins (Ellis, 2013; Graham-Rowe, 2011). In addition, variations in the quality of herbal ingredients and limited regulation of herbal medicine in some countries raise concerns regarding public safety. Reports have documented cases in which patients have suffered severe adverse effects following certain treatments (Sample, 2010). Despite these controversies, criticism of TCM remains politically sensitive within China. Because TCM is closely linked to national identity and cultural heritage, questioning its scientific legitimacy is often perceived as challenging broader nationalist sentiments (Stone, 2008).

Nevertheless, the global popularity of TCM has continued to grow. The World Health Organization (WHO) has recognised TCM within its international medical classification systems, contributing to its increasing global visibility (Cyranoski, 2018). In addition, the Chinese government has invested heavily in the modernisation and international promotion of TCM. For example, in 2010 the Chinese state allocated approximately 4.9 billion RMB to support the development of the TCM industry (Cheung, 2011). Interest in TCM has expanded

further following the emergence of Covid-19, with several studies suggesting that certain TCM treatments may help alleviate severe symptoms of the disease (Li et al., 2020; Ren et al., 2020; Xu and Zhang, 2020). Some proponents have even argued that TCM represents one of the most effective approaches for preventing and treating Covid-19 (Zhao et al., 2021). These claims remain contested, but the debate surrounding TCM has important implications for China's global reputation.

Over the past decade, China's rapid economic development has attracted significant international attention. However, its authoritarian political system has also generated criticism and has negatively affected China's international image (Shambaugh, 2015). In response, the Chinese government has invested in a range of sectors—including media, education, culture, sports, and the arts—in an effort to cultivate and expand its soft power (Eliküçük Yıldırım and Aslan, 2020; Shambaugh, 2015). Within this broader strategy, the international promotion of Traditional Chinese Medicine has emerged as a potentially important instrument of cultural diplomacy and global influence.

Introduction to Soft Power and Its Definition in the Context of China

Soft power is defined as the “ability to affect others to obtain the outcome one wants through attraction, rather than coercion or payment” (Watanabe et al., 2008). The concept was originally developed by Joseph Nye, an American political scientist and diplomat. Nye (1990) argues that soft power involves shaping the preferences of other nations through attraction rather than force. As China continues its rapid economic rise, the concept of soft power has become an increasingly important concern among Chinese political elites and scholars (Mingjiang, 2008). In contrast, hard power refers to the ability of a state to compel others to act in a desired manner through military strength, economic leverage, or coercive diplomatic pressure (Wilson, 2008). Despite China's impressive military capabilities and economic influence, many scholars argue that China's soft power remains relatively underdeveloped and is still in an early stage of development (Mingjiang, 2008; Shambaugh, 2015).

This raises questions about what factors contribute to the cultivation of a country's soft power. Nye (2011) argues that a country's soft power derives primarily from its culture, political values, and foreign policy. According to Nye, attraction is generated when other states perceive a country's political system and foreign policy as legitimate and worthy of trust. However, Nye's conceptualisation of soft power assumes a political environment in which a clear distinction exists between state and non-state actors. This assumption does not easily apply to China's political system, where the state plays a dominant role in shaping cultural,

political, and social activities (Shambaugh, 2015). As a result, scholars have argued that Nye's "classical" framework cannot fully explain how soft power operates in the Chinese context. Consequently, alternative theoretical approaches have been proposed in order to better analyse China's soft power strategies (Eliküçük Yıldırım and Aslan, 2020).

In response to these limitations, Eliküçük Yıldırım and Aslan (2020) introduce the concept of defensive image-protection strategies as a component of soft power. These strategies aim to protect a country's reputation and counter negative perceptions in the international arena. They contrast with Nye's "classical" offensive soft power strategies, which involve the active promotion and dissemination of cultural goods, institutions, and political narratives. According to Eliküçük Yıldırım and Aslan (2020), China's international reputation has been challenged by criticism of its authoritarian political system, strict control over media and cultural expression, and reports of human rights violations (Shambaugh, 2015). In addition, China's rapid economic expansion and growing military capabilities have generated concern among other states regarding its long-term strategic intentions (Medeiros, 2009). These developments have contributed to negative international perceptions of China.

In response to these challenges, China has adopted a combination of offensive and defensive soft power strategies. Offensive strategies include the production and distribution of cultural goods, the establishment of international institutions, and the dissemination of political narratives. However, Eliküçük Yıldırım and Aslan (2020) argue that these strategies alone are insufficient for improving China's international image. Defensive strategies must also be employed in order to counter negative perceptions and manage China's global reputation. Thus, when evaluating China's soft power, it is necessary to consider not only what is actively promoted but also what narratives are suppressed or reframed (Eliküçük Yıldırım and Aslan, 2020, p.165). By combining both defensive and offensive strategies, China seeks to present itself as a cooperative and non-threatening global actor while simultaneously advancing its economic development, sovereignty, and international status—three key objectives of Chinese foreign policy (Medeiros, 2009).

Eliküçük Yıldırım and Aslan (2020) further argue that China adopts different soft power strategies depending on whether the target audience is located in the developing or developed world. In developing countries, China primarily employs offensive strategies designed to highlight its economic success and development experience. These strategies include the exportation of China's development model, foreign aid, investment, foreign policy initiatives, the promotion of traditional culture, and international broadcasting. These strategies are highly visible and are intended to project an image of strength and capability.

By contrast, China adopts more defensive image-protection strategies when engaging with developed countries. In these contexts, China seeks to present itself as approachable and non-threatening. This is often achieved through investments, cultural exchange initiatives, and international broadcasting that promote positive aspects of Chinese culture while downplaying concerns about China's growing economic and political influence. Through these strategies, China attempts to mitigate fears associated with its rapid rise while maintaining positive diplomatic and economic relationships.

Several scholars support similar interpretations of China's soft power strategy. Shambaugh (2015), for example, highlights the role of media, education, sports, the arts, infrastructure projects, and diplomacy in China's efforts to cultivate soft power. Initiatives such as the global expansion of Confucius Institutes and the promotion of Chinese cultural traditions through arts and sporting events serve to enhance China's cultural visibility. In addition, China's foreign policy initiatives—particularly infrastructure projects associated with the Belt and Road Initiatives (BRI)—also contribute to the expansion of China's international influence.

Vuving (2009) offers another influential perspective by identifying what he calls the three “currencies” of soft power: beauty, brilliance, and benignity. Beauty refers to the attraction generated by a country's culture and values; brilliance reflects admiration for a country's political system, economic achievements, or development model; and benignity arises from perceptions of generosity and goodwill, such as those created through foreign aid. According to Vuving (2009), these attributes may be cultivated through various mechanisms, including cultural exchange, economic assistance, and diplomatic engagement. International broadcasting, in particular, can serve as a vehicle through which these soft power currencies are communicated to global audiences.

Mingjiang (2008) similarly emphasises the importance of China's defensive image-protection strategies. He argues that China increasingly seeks to counter negative international narratives and reshape global perceptions of its rise. Ultimately, the literature discussed above suggests that China's soft power strategy is strongly linked to the management and cultivation of its international image. While China aims to present itself as a peaceful and cooperative global power, it must simultaneously respond to criticism and protect its reputation both domestically and internationally. This dynamic provides the broader context within which the international promotion of Traditional Chinese Medicine can be examined as a potential instrument of China's soft power strategy.

These theoretical perspectives suggest that China employs a combination of offensive and defensive soft power strategies in order to shape international perceptions of its rise. The

following section therefore examines whether the international promotion of Traditional Chinese Medicine functions as one such strategy within China's broader soft power framework.

Hypothesis and Argument

This study hypothesises that Traditional Chinese Medicine (TCM) is indirectly utilised as a tool for cultivating China's soft power. Specifically, the analysis adopts Eliküçük Yıldırım and Aslan's (2020) framework of soft power tools in order to examine how the international promotion of TCM contributes to China's broader soft power strategy.

To test this hypothesis, two case studies are examined: the Covid-19 pandemic and the BRI. It is argued that both the global health crisis and the development of the BRI have facilitated the integration, promotion, distribution, and consumption of TCM at an international level. These developments provide opportunities for the Chinese state to promote TCM in ways that simultaneously enhance China's global image.

The selection of the Covid-19 pandemic and the BRI as case studies is based on the argument that the promotion of TCM within these contexts is relatively politically neutral, economically advantageous, and less likely to generate significant international dispute (Kuah, 2021). In the context of the pandemic, TCM has been promoted as a potential treatment for Covid-19, enabling China to distribute medical assistance abroad while promoting its traditional medical practices. Similarly, within the BRI framework, TCM has been promoted as a form of cultural exchange and international cooperation. Through these mechanisms, it is possible for China to present TCM both as a medical resource and as a cultural commodity.

By analysing these two case studies, this study aims to demonstrate the extension to which the promotion of TCM contributes to the cultivation of China's soft power. At the same time, the analysis considers both supportive and critical perspectives surrounding TCM, providing a balanced examination of how it is interpreted, understood, and utilised within international political discourse. Thus, this study contributes to existing scholarship on China's soft power by examining the role of Traditional Chinese Medicine (TCM) as a potential instrument of cultural and diplomatic influence. While previous research has explored China's use of cultural diplomacy, media expansion, and economic initiatives to enhance its international image, relatively less attention has been paid to the role of TCM within this broader strategy. By analysing the promotion of TCM during the Covid-19 pandemic and its integration into the BRI, this study highlights how medical knowledge and cultural heritage can function as mechanisms of soft power. In doing so, the study demonstrates that TCM

operates not only as a healthcare practice but also as a form of cultural diplomacy embedded within China's broader international engagement.

Various soft power tools and strategies of China

Many scholars follow the same line of argument as Eliküçük Yıldırım and Aslan (2020); however, some scholars emphasise offensive strategies more than the defensive image protection strategies China adopts to cultivate its soft power. For instance, Shambaugh (2015) explains how media, sports, the arts, education, infrastructure, and diplomacy all play a part in China's attempt to improve its soft power. From Chinese martial artists to the establishment of Confucius Institutes, the arts, sports, and education are used to promote Chinese traditional culture. Additionally, China's foreign policy highlights the role that host diplomacy as well as the BRI and other infrastructures play in China's foreign policy, generating China's soft power. Regarding defensive strategies, Shambaugh (2015) highlights the role of China's increasing global media presence in creating a positive reputation and fending off negative comments. Vuving (2009) suggests that since soft power is the power to generate attraction, such attributes must be taken into consideration. He summarises the attributes of "beauty, brilliance and benignity" into "soft power currencies" (Vuving, 2009, p.7). These soft power tools are predominantly similar to those of Shambaugh (2015), but adds references to myths, economic assistance, and aid. Also, Vuving (*ibid.*) states the currencies can cultivate soft power, directly or indirectly, and through one or multiple soft power currencies. He goes on to propose that a country can cultivate its soft power first by displaying its beauty through the demonstration of its traditional culture; second, through its brilliance, which can be evidenced through the exportation of a country's development model, investment, and foreign policy; and third, through a country's benignity, which is seen through activities such as foreign aid and exporting the country's development model. International broadcasting can be used as a vehicle for all soft power currencies (*ibid.*).

Mingjiang (2008) discusses the discourse around China's soft power and highlights China's defensive image protection strategies in the same way as Eliküçük Yıldırım and Aslan (2020), emphasising the defensive approach taken by China to protect its global image by rebuking negative misconceptions, and repelling any unwanted counterattacks. These scholars propose that China's soft power is almost entirely reliant on cultivating and defending a positive international image. While China wants to demonstrate that it is a peaceful superpower that plays by the rules of the international arena, it also wants to protect its image on both domestic and international levels.

One hypothesis proposed in this study is that TCM is indirectly used to cultivate China's soft power through Eliküçük Yıldırım and Aslan's (2020) definition of soft power. The hypothesis is tested by examining two case studies: the Covid-19 pandemic and the BRI. It is suggested that the pandemic and BRI development facilitated the integration, promotion, distribution, and consumption of TCM. The pandemic and the BRI were chosen as case studies as promoting TCM in these contexts is politically neutral, economically advantageous, and less disputable (Kuah, 2021). These two case studies effectively support this hypothesis because by integrating TCM as a form of Covid-19 treatment and as a cultural commodity along the BRI, China can achieve a positive image without much controversy.

As the study explores the role of TCM in cultivating China's soft power, it simultaneously presents key arguments for and against TCM from a neutral perspective.

First, it is imperative to understand how TCM is interpreted, understood, and utilised. The remainder of this study is structured as follows. The next section provides a background to Traditional Chinese Medicine and outlines the key debates surrounding its efficacy and global expansion. The following two sections present case studies analysing the promotion of TCM during the Covid-19 pandemic and the integration of TCM into the BRI. The final section summarises the findings and reflects on the implications for understanding China's use of soft power.

Background of TCM and contemporary debates

As outlined in the introduction, Traditional Chinese Medicine (TCM) is an integral component of Chinese culture and medical practice. This section provides an overview of TCM, including the philosophical foundations that underpin it, the principles through which it is believed to operate, and the reasons why it remains a subject of ongoing debate. Understanding these aspects provides an important foundation for analysing how TCM may be utilised as a tool of soft power by the Chinese government.

TCM encompasses a range of medical practices, including acupuncture, herbal remedies, cupping, moxibustion, and massage therapy known as *Tui Na* (Hesketh and Zhu, 1997; Xu and Xia, 2019). These practices date back several thousand years and remain widely used both within China and internationally (Keji and Hao, 2003; Xu and Yang, 2009). Many classical medical texts continue to play a central role in the study and practice of TCM today. For example, *Huangdi Neijing* (The Yellow Emperor's Inner Canon), believed to have been written during the Warring States period (476–221 BC), remains one of the most influential

texts in the TCM tradition (Cheung, 2011). These early works continue to shape contemporary understandings of TCM theory and practice.

The philosophical foundations of TCM are closely linked to the traditions of Buddhism, Confucianism, and Taoism, which emphasise the interconnectedness of human beings and the natural world (Keji and Hao, 2003; Xu and Xia, 2019). Within TCM theory, the human body is understood as a system governed by the flow of *qi*—a vital form of energy—and the dynamic balance between *yin* and *yang*, the complementary forces of nature (Xu and Xia, 2019). *Qi* is believed to circulate through pathways known as meridians, regulating the body's physiological functions (China's State Council Information Office of the People's Republic of China, 2016; Keji and Hao, 2003). Illness is therefore understood as a disruption in the balance of these forces or an obstruction in the flow of *qi*. TCM treatments seek to restore equilibrium by correcting imbalances between *yin* and *yang* and regulating the circulation of *qi* throughout the body.

These concepts are further elaborated through the theory of the Five Elements (*Wu Xing*), which associates bodily organ systems with the elements of wood, fire, earth, metal, and water (Keji and Hao, 2003; Wang and Zhu, 2011). According to this theory, the liver, heart, lungs, kidneys, and spleen correspond to these elements and influence both physiological and psychological processes. Changes in the interaction between these elements are believed to affect health and well-being. Each element is also associated with its seasons, emotions, tastes, colours, and sensory experiences, reflecting the broader cosmological framework within which TCM operates (Wang and Zhu, 2011).

Efforts have been made to condense all the knowledge and theories into one established and neat classical system in order to simplify all the knowledge and ancient theories of TCM that date back thousands of years (Leung *et al.*, 2006; Qiu, 2007). However, given the complexity of these philosophical foundations, many aspects of TCM are difficult to evaluate using conventional scientific methodologies. This has contributed to ongoing controversies surrounding the legitimacy and efficacy of TCM. One major difference between TCM and Western biomedicine lies in their respective approaches to disease. Western medicine typically focuses on diagnosing and treating specific pathological conditions, whereas TCM emphasises the holistic balance of the body as a whole. Consequently, TCM is often viewed as a preventative system of medicine and is frequently applied to chronic conditions or illnesses for which established biomedical treatments may be limited (Stone, 2008; Xu and Xia, 2019). From the perspective of TCM philosophy, a localised illness is often interpreted as evidence of a broader systemic imbalance within the body (Sun *et al.*, 2013).

Further controversies arise from the methods used in TCM treatments. Herbal prescriptions commonly contain numerous ingredients; it is not unusual for a single prescription to include more than ten different herbs (Kuah, 2021). These ingredients are typically combined and boiled to produce medicinal extracts for consumption. In contrast, Western biomedical research generally focuses on isolating individual compounds and testing them through controlled clinical trials (Hesketh and Zhu, 1997; Leung et al., 2006; Tang, 2006; Tang et al., 1999). Because the specific chemical compounds and mechanisms within many TCM treatments cannot be easily isolated, critics argue that their efficacy is difficult to verify scientifically. In addition, variations in herbal quality, environmental contaminants, and dosage inconsistencies can raise concerns regarding safety. Reports of adverse reactions and deaths associated with certain treatments have further intensified these debates (Sample, 2010; Pinghui, 2016). As a result, many non-practitioners remain sceptical of TCM despite its long historical tradition.

Nevertheless, attempts have been made to demonstrate the scientific value of TCM. One notable example is the work of Chinese pharmaceutical chemist Tu Youyou, who received the Nobel Prize in Physiology or Medicine in 2015 for her discovery of artemisinin, an antimalarial compound derived from traditional herbal medicine (Tu, 2011). Tu's discovery was inspired by ancient Chinese medical texts describing the use of wormwood to treat symptoms associated with malaria (The Nobel Prize, 2015). This breakthrough is frequently cited as evidence that traditional medical knowledge can contribute to modern biomedical discoveries. In addition, the World Health Organization included traditional medicine originating from TCM in the eleventh revision of the International Classification of Diseases in 2018, reflecting its growing international recognition (Xinhua, 2016). Despite these developments, debates regarding the efficacy and scientific validity of TCM remain ongoing.

The practice of TCM is not limited to mainland China. It has long been used throughout East Asia and has become an increasingly important global industry. In mainland China and Hong Kong, approximately sixty per cent of the population has sought treatment from a TCM practitioner, while in countries such as Japan, South Korea, Singapore, and Taiwan between sixty and seventy-five per cent of the population reportedly use TCM at least occasionally (Cheung, 2011). Since the economic reforms initiated by Deng Xiaoping in 1978, the TCM industry has expanded rapidly both domestically and internationally (Xu and Xia, 2019). For example, in 2010 the Chinese government invested approximately 4.9 billion RMB in the development of the TCM industry (Cheung, 2011). By 2015, the output value of China's TCM pharmaceutical industry had reached 786.6 billion RMB, accounting for 28.55 per cent of the

country's pharmaceutical sector (Xu and Xia, 2019). International trade in Chinese medicinal products has also remained substantial, with exports estimated at approximately \$3.72 billion in 2015 (Xinhua, 2016). The global TCM market, including both products and services, has been estimated to exceed \$50 billion (Juan, 2017).

Foreign pharmaceutical companies have also demonstrated growing interest in TCM research. For instance, GlaxoSmithKline has established research and development centres in China in search of new pharmaceutical compounds derived from traditional medicines, following the successful discovery of artemisinin. According to the State Council of the People's Republic of China, TCM products and practices are now used in more than 180 countries and regions worldwide (Xinhua, 2016).

Since the Mao era, the Chinese government has actively supported the development and promotion of TCM. One reason for this support is the comparatively high cost associated with Western biomedical treatments (Stone, 2008). In contrast, TCM has historically provided a more cost-effective means of delivering healthcare services to large populations. In addition, the cultivation of medicinal herbs has contributed to rural economic development by increasing farmers' incomes and supporting agricultural diversification (Xu and Xia, 2019). As a result, TCM has played an important role not only in China's healthcare system but also in its broader economic development.

In summary, despite persistent debates surrounding its efficacy and safety, TCM remains one of the world's oldest and most widely practiced medical systems. Its international visibility continues to increase as the Chinese government actively promotes and distributes TCM worldwide. Against this background, this study examines whether the international promotion of TCM functions as a mechanism through which China seeks to cultivate soft power. To explore this question, two case studies are examined: China's response to the Covid-19 pandemic and the BRI.s These cases provide insight into how TCM has been promoted both domestically and internationally, allowing an evaluation of its role within China's broader soft power strategy.

These debates surrounding the legitimacy, safety, and international promotion of TCM provide an important context for analysing how the Chinese state has incorporated TCM into its broader soft power strategy. The following sections examine two key cases in which TCM has been promoted internationally: the Covid-19 pandemic and the BRI.

Case Study 1: Covid-19

The emergence of the Covid-19 pandemic created new opportunities for China to cultivate soft power. As the novel coronavirus spread globally, governments implemented border closures and lockdown measures while medical experts sought effective treatments. During this period, Traditional Chinese Medicine (TCM) was promoted within China as a complementary treatment for Covid-19, and it subsequently gained international attention.

This section examines how Chinese officials used the pandemic as an opportunity to promote TCM and demonstrate its effectiveness. In particular, the Chinese government highlighted treatment protocols that combined TCM with Western biomedicine, reporting favourable recovery outcomes among patients who received such treatments. At the same time, international media outlets associated with the Chinese state circulated narratives emphasising the role of TCM in China's response to the pandemic. However, despite these claims, scepticism regarding the efficacy of TCM remained widespread.

One of the major criticisms of TCM concerns the lack of evidence-based clinical validation. In response, Chinese authorities attempted to strengthen the legitimacy of TCM by incorporating it into official treatment protocols for Covid-19. The seventh and eighth versions of China's *Diagnosis and Treatment Protocol for Covid-19* included more than eighteen recommended TCM medicines for prevention and treatment (Lyu et al., 2021). Among the most widely promoted was Jinhua Qinggan granules, a patented TCM formulation recommended as part of Covid-19 treatment guidelines (ibid). The National Health Commission also issued treatment plans that encouraged the combined use of TCM and Western biomedicine ('Notification on the diagnosis and treatment plan for pneumonia caused by the novel coronavirus', 2020).

However, the integration of TCM with Western medicine generated additional controversy. Critics argued that recovery among patients receiving combined treatments did not necessarily demonstrate the efficacy of TCM itself. Some commentators suggested that TCM functioned merely as a supplementary treatment rather than a scientifically validated therapy. Western media outlets often expressed scepticism toward these claims. For example, a *New York Times* article titled "*In Coronavirus, China Weighs Benefits of Buffalo Horn and Other Remedies*" highlighted unusual ingredients used in TCM while questioning its effectiveness (Wee, 2020).

In response to such criticism, Chinese officials published statistics emphasising the role of TCM in China's pandemic response. Reports indicated that more than 90 per cent of the approximately 70,000 Covid-19 patients treated in China had received TCM in combination with Western medicine. While the World Health Organization estimated that roughly 13 per

cent of Covid-19 cases globally became severe, China's National Health Commission reported that fewer than 5 per cent of cases in Chinese hospitals developed into serious conditions (Johnson, 2021). Chinese authorities attributed this comparatively low severity rate in part to the integration of TCM into treatment protocols.

Alongside these statistics, Chinese media outlets intensified international coverage highlighting the role of TCM in combating Covid-19. English-language platforms such as *Xinhua*, *China Daily*, and the *South China Morning Post* published numerous reports describing the success of TCM treatments in efforts to demonstrate how TCM has been used to “turn a natural disaster into a triumph” (Waterson and Kuo, 2020). For instance, *China Daily* reported that Lianhua Qingwen capsules—one of the Chinese medicines distributed internationally—could help inhibit viral infection and improve recovery rates (‘Traditional Chinese medicine aids Italy in fighting Covid-19’, 2020). Similarly, reports published by *Xinhuanet* emphasised the effectiveness of combining TCM with Western medicine in reducing mortality rates (Huaxia, 2020). Some academic studies also supported these claims, suggesting that TCM treatments may help improve recovery outcomes among Covid-19 patients (Xia et al., 2021), although potential bias should be acknowledged, as some researchers received funding from Chinese government institutions.

These efforts illustrate the importance of international broadcasting in China's soft power strategy. According to Eliküçük Yıldırım and Aslan (2020), international broadcasting directed at developed countries functions as a defensive image-protection strategy. By disseminating narratives highlighting China's success in managing the pandemic—particularly through the integration of TCM—Chinese authorities sought to strengthen the country's global reputation. Media reports emphasising low mortality rates and successful treatment outcomes were therefore used not only to promote TCM but also to demonstrate the effectiveness of China's political and healthcare systems.

In addition to media promotion, China also exported TCM treatments and expertise to countries affected by the pandemic. During Covid-19, Chinese medical teams distributed TCM medicines, provided training to local healthcare workers, and established TCM treatment centres in several developing countries. For example, TCM clinics were established in Zimbabwe, where local populations gained access to affordable treatment options (Huaxia, 2021). Similarly, Chinese medical experts travelled to Cambodia to provide assistance and training in TCM-based treatments for Covid-19 patients (Huaxia, 2022). According to Huang Luqi, Vice-Commissioner of the National Administration of Traditional Chinese Medicine, these initiatives were intended to strengthen the capacity of foreign medical personnel to treat

Covid-19 using TCM methods (China to dispatch experts of traditional Chinese medicine to Cambodia to fight Covid-19, 2022).

These activities reflect several mechanisms through which TCM contributed to the cultivation of China's soft power during the pandemic. First, the distribution of TCM medicines and medical expertise functioned as a form of foreign aid directed primarily toward developing countries. According to Eliküçük Yıldırım and Aslan (2020), foreign aid constitutes an offensive soft power strategy that allows states to demonstrate capability and leadership. By providing medical assistance through TCM treatments and training programmes, China positioned itself as a provider of humanitarian support during a global crisis.

Second, the international promotion of TCM can be interpreted as a form of exporting China's development model. Vuving (2009) argues that countries may enhance their attractiveness by demonstrating the effectiveness of their political and economic systems. Through the global promotion of TCM as part of its pandemic response, China implicitly presented its governance model and medical practices as effective solutions to global health challenges. In doing so, China sought to demonstrate the "brilliance" of its political system and development strategy.

Third, international broadcasting played a crucial role in shaping global perceptions of these initiatives. By reporting extensively on China's medical assistance and the effectiveness of TCM treatments, Chinese media outlets constructed narratives portraying China as a responsible and cooperative global actor. Within Vuving's (2009) framework, such narratives emphasise two key soft power currencies: brilliance and benignity. Brilliance is conveyed through China's capacity to provide medical knowledge and effective treatment strategies, while benignity is demonstrated through the provision of humanitarian assistance to other countries.

Taken together, these developments illustrate how both offensive and defensive soft power strategies were employed during the Covid-19 pandemic. Through the international promotion and distribution of TCM, China sought to cultivate an image of generosity, competence, and technological capability. In this way, TCM functioned not only as a medical treatment but also as a diplomatic instrument through which China attempted to strengthen its global reputation.

The international expansion of TCM has also been supported by the BRI. Since the launch of the BRI, more than forty TCM centres have been established across thirty-five countries (The State Council Information Office of the People's Republic of China, 2019). Plans have also been announced to construct additional hospitals, research centres, and

educational institutions dedicated to TCM along the BRI network (Chen, 2018). The integration of TCM into the BRI therefore represents another important avenue through which China seeks to expand its cultural and diplomatic influence. The following section examines this process in greater detail.

The international distribution of Traditional Chinese Medicine (TCM) during the Covid-19 pandemic can be understood as a mechanism through which China sought to cultivate soft power. In particular, the promotion and exportation of TCM enabled China to project an image of competence, generosity, and global leadership. Three soft power strategies are especially visible in this process: the provision of foreign aid, the exportation of a development model, and the use of international broadcasting.

Within the framework proposed by Eliküçük Yıldırım and Aslan (2020), these strategies contribute to the enhancement of China's international attractiveness by presenting the country as both capable and cooperative. Through the global distribution and promotion of TCM treatments, China simultaneously provides humanitarian assistance, demonstrates the effectiveness of its governance model, and promotes narratives that portray the Chinese state as a responsible actor in global health governance. As a result, TCM functions not only as a medical intervention but also as a diplomatic and cultural instrument through which China cultivates soft power.

The Covid-19 pandemic therefore provided a unique opportunity for China to promote Traditional Chinese Medicine internationally while simultaneously strengthening its soft power through medical assistance, international broadcasting, and the provision of healthcare support to other countries. However, China's promotion of TCM is not limited to the context of global health crises. The integration of TCM into long-term international initiatives, particularly the BRI, further illustrates how China seeks to institutionalise the global expansion of TCM. The following case study therefore examines how TCM has been incorporated into the BRI as part of China's broader strategy for cultivating soft power.

Case study 2: The Belt and Road Initiative (BRI)

While the Covid-19 pandemic provided an immediate context in which China promoted Traditional Chinese Medicine internationally, the global expansion of TCM is also embedded within longer-term strategic initiatives. One of the most significant of these initiatives is the BRI, launched by President Xi Jinping in 2013. The BRI provides an institutional and infrastructural framework through which China can promote economic cooperation, cultural exchange, and medical collaboration with countries across Asia, Europe, Africa, and the Middle

East. Within this broader framework, TCM has increasingly been incorporated as both a cultural and economic component of China's international engagement.

In 2013, Xi Jinping launched the BRI, a transnational infrastructure and connectivity project involving 130 countries (China Belt and Road Network, 2022) and over 60 per cent of the world's population (Ruta, 2018). Through the development of port and rail infrastructure, the BRI is expected to facilitate trade and connectivity across technological, economic, and cultural spheres (Kuah, 2021). More broadly, it encourages trade, introduces new financial and regulatory frameworks, and promotes exchange in areas such as tourism, education, economics, and medicine (Hinsley et al., 2020). By 2017, China had already invested \$124 billion in the BRI (BBC, 2017), including \$50 billion in the Asian Infrastructure Investment Bank, equivalent to half of the bank's capital (Weiss, 2017).

The BRI has been interpreted in several ways. Kuah (2021) suggests that it may be understood as a shift in China's foreign policy (Aoyama, 2016), a geo-economic project designed to integrate China more deeply into the global economy (Li, 2020), and an attempt to expand China's presence in the international arena. It has also been described as a platform for the exercise of cultural power, as it creates opportunities for exchange between China and populations along the BRI corridor (Kuah, 2021). Xi Jinping's emphasis on "policy, infrastructure, trade, financial, and people-to-people connectivity" (Xi, 2017) reflects this broader vision, with "people-to-people connectivity" encompassing education, culture, and scientific exchange (OECD Business and Finance Outlook, 2018). These objectives are reflected in official policies, plans, and laws, including those relating to the promotion, trade, and consumption of TCM along BRI routes.

How China is using TCM in the BRI to accumulate soft power

As TCM has been integrated into the BRI, it has also become a tool through which China seeks to cultivate soft power. Nye (1990) argues that foreign policy can generate soft power when it is viewed by other countries as legitimate and worthy of respect. Medeiros (2009) similarly notes that China's foreign policy is oriented towards creating conditions that enhance development, sovereignty, and international status. In this context, the incorporation of TCM into BRI policy can be interpreted not merely as a health or trade initiative, but as part of a broader effort to strengthen China's international image and influence.

Policies established for the implementation of TCM along the BRI promote not only educational, cultural, technological, and commercial exchange, but also scientific exchange (CQNEWS, 2017). Under this broader category, the Chinese state has considered integrating

TCM into the global health system through BRI-related policy frameworks (Yao, Shen, and Li, 2019). By embedding TCM in the BRI, China simultaneously advances globalisation through a culturally distinctive commodity and elevates TCM as both an economic and medical resource (Kuah, 2021). This is significant for soft power because the wider the circulation and acceptance of TCM, the greater the opportunity for China to project cultural value, policy effectiveness, and international leadership.

To facilitate this process, a range of plans, policies, and laws have been introduced. The *Development Plan of the Belt and Road for Traditional Chinese Medicine (2016–2020)* proposed four major systems: an international medical service system, an international education and cultural communication system, a science and technology system, and an international trade system for TCM (Kuah, 2021). The plan aimed to establish 30 TCM centres worldwide, 20 of which would adopt international TCM standards, license 100 TCM ingredients, and create 50 TCM exchange and cooperation centres by 2020 (Traditional Knowledge Data Base, 2017). These measures provide clear evidence that the Chinese state has actively created institutional channels through which TCM can be standardised, circulated, and promoted internationally.

Additional support for this expansion was provided through the *National Drug Circulation Industry Plan (2016–2020)* issued by the Chinese Ministry of Commerce (Department of Market Order, Ministry of Commerce, 2018), which encouraged countries along the BRI to establish TCM hospitals and adopt common TCM standards (Kuah, 2021). Wang Xiaopin, Director of the International Cooperation Department at the State Administration of TCM, stated that these projects were intended to facilitate cooperation and development in fields such as TCM services, free trade, pharmaceuticals, scientific research, and cultural and educational exchange (Juan, 2017). In 2019, infrastructure investment and trade development relating to the promotion of TCM were also approved by the State Council of the People's Republic of China (Juan, 2017).

These infrastructure projects appear to have generated measurable outcomes. Since the launch of the BRI, more than 40 TCM centres have been established in over 30 countries (The State Council Information Office of the People's Republic of China, 2019). In addition, profits from TCM products reportedly increased by 54 per cent between 2016 and 2017 (Cyranoski, 2018). By 2020, plans to extend TCM infrastructure further into the Middle East and Europe were also underway (Hinsley et al., 2020). These developments suggest that the BRI has provided an effective institutional framework for expanding the global reach of TCM.

The international promotion of TCM has also depended on processes of standardisation. In order for TCM to circulate more widely through BRI networks, common standards, logistical systems, and quality-control mechanisms have been required. Kuah (2021) notes that relevant initiatives have included the *Guidelines for the Planning and Construction of the National Herbal Medicine Logistics Base*, the *White Paper for China's Traditional Chinese Medicine*, and the *Chinese Medicine Law*. The State Council has also introduced the *Outline of Chinese Medicine Development Strategy Plan 2016–2030*, aimed at improving the quality control of TCM commodities for both domestic and international markets (Kuah, 2021). These measures are important because they attempt to address one of the main criticisms of TCM—its inconsistency—and thereby support its wider acceptance abroad.

The integration of TCM into the BRI also relates directly to the exportation of China's development model and the promotion of traditional culture. In order to help countries along the BRI “learn from China's development experience” (OECD Business and Finance Outlook, 2018, p.4), Xi Jinping launched the Centre for Knowledge on Development as well as China's *National Plan on Implementation of the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development* (Chinese Government, 2016). These initiatives promote educational, cultural, and scientific exchange across the BRI region (OECD Business and Finance Outlook, 2018). Within these exchanges, TCM is positioned not only as a medical practice but also as a cultural and developmental resource. The *13th Five-Year Plan* also emphasised TCM as a form of cultural exchange alongside education, science, technology, sports, and tourism (OECD Business and Outlook, 2018). In this sense, the promotion of TCM through the BRI may be interpreted as a means of exporting both a form of medical assistance and a development model associated with China's economic rise. As Eliküçük Yıldırım and Aslan (2020) argue, such strategies may be particularly attractive to developing countries seeking models of growth and development.

TCM also carries symbolic value as a component of Chinese heritage. Because it originated in China and has long been embedded in Chinese culture (Keji and Hao, 2003), it can be framed as a form of national heritage and therefore as a source of cultural prestige (Stone, 2008). Liu (2020) argues that the BRI provides a platform for constructing a recognisable “brand” of Chinese medicine culture, thereby highlighting the distinctive appeal of Chinese civilisation. In the *Journal of the Chinese People's Political Consultative Conference*, it is similarly argued that the BRI enables Chinese medicine culture to function as a marker of China's cultural soft power (Liu, 2020). Within Eliküçük Yıldırım and Aslan's (2020) framework, the promotion of traditional culture can function as both an offensive and a

defensive soft power strategy. It is offensive insofar as it projects attraction and cultural confidence; it is defensive insofar as it helps shift attention away from concerns associated with China's hard power. By promoting TCM through scientific and cultural exchange, the Chinese state therefore reinforces its image as both culturally rich and internationally cooperative.

This dynamic can also be understood in relation to other forms of cultural soft power. Just as the international circulation of cultural products such as anime can generate wider interest in a country's language, values, and traditions, the growing global consumption of TCM may similarly increase curiosity about China and its cultural heritage. At the same time, whether the promotion of traditions and cultural values ultimately translates into broader attraction remains contested (Albert, 2018).

Overall, the integration of TCM into the BRI demonstrates how the Chinese state uses policy, infrastructure, and cultural exchange to cultivate soft power. TCM has been established not only as "an important health commodity" but also as an integral "part of the cultural and intangible Chinese heritage" (Kuah, 2021, p.225). As China promotes TCM through BRI-related plans and institutions, it simultaneously advances several soft power mechanisms identified in the theoretical literature. First, it exports a development model by presenting Chinese approaches to medicine, governance, and modernisation as effective and transferable. Second, it promotes traditional culture, thereby demonstrating what Vuving (2009) describes as beauty. Third, insofar as TCM is framed as a form of medical assistance and cooperation, it also carries elements of benignity. These strategies in turn support broader foreign policy goals related to development, sovereignty, and international status (Medeiros, 2009).

TCM distribution through the BRI therefore functions as more than a health or trade initiative. It operates as a diplomatic and cultural mechanism through which China seeks to enhance its international reputation and influence. In this way, the BRI case study supports the argument that TCM is being used to cultivate China's soft power through a combination of foreign policy, development strategy, cultural promotion, and international cooperation.

Conclusion

This study set out to examine the extent to which Traditional Chinese Medicine (TCM) is being utilised as a tool through which China cultivates soft power. Drawing on soft power theory and analysing two case studies—the promotion of TCM during the Covid-19 pandemic and the integration of TCM into the BRI—this study has demonstrated that TCM functions not only as a medical practice but also as a cultural and diplomatic instrument within China's broader international strategy.

The Covid-19 case study illustrated how China promoted TCM internationally through medical assistance, international broadcasting, and the distribution of treatments to countries affected by the pandemic. These actions contributed to narratives portraying China as a capable and cooperative global actor.

The BRI case study demonstrated how TCM has been institutionalised within long-term international initiatives through policies, infrastructure development, and cultural exchange programmes. Through these mechanisms, TCM is promoted as both a medical resource and a component of Chinese cultural heritage.

When interpreted through the framework of soft power theory, these developments illustrate how TCM contributes to the projection of what Vuving (2009) describes as beauty, brilliance, and benignity. TCM reflects cultural heritage (beauty), demonstrates perceived effectiveness of Chinese governance and development models (brilliance), and is often presented as a form of humanitarian assistance (benignity). In this way, TCM serves as an indirect mechanism through which China seeks to enhance its international attractiveness and influence.

Overall, the findings suggest that the international promotion of TCM should be understood not only as a medical or economic development but also as part of a broader strategy of cultural diplomacy. As China continues to expand its global presence through initiatives such as the BRI, the role of TCM within its soft power strategy is likely to become increasingly significant. Further research may therefore examine how the international reception of TCM evolves and how it shapes perceptions of China in different regional contexts.

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